

Netherlands Food and Consumer
Product Safety Authority
Ministry of Agriculture,
Nature and Food Quality

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To the Head of Agency of the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority

Advice of the Director of the Office for Risk Assessment & Research

Advice on the implementation of the National Residues Plan: supplementary advice on residues in horse, goat, sheep and milk.

Office for Risk Assessment & Research

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Background

The National Residues Plan (NPR) in products of animal origin is the Dutch elaboration of Directive 96/22/EC¹ and 96/23/EC². This Directive specifies which groups of substances the Member States are required to include in their annual monitoring of animal products. As such, the NPR is an important cornerstone for the free movement of animal products within the EU and for the export of animal products outside the EU. At the end of 2022, Directive 96/23/EC will be repealed and replaced by Regulation EU 2017/625³. In addition to the specified compulsory controls, this new regulation offers more space for additional risk-based controls by the Member States.

In 2017, the Office for Risk Assessment & Research (BuRO) commissioned WFSR⁴ to develop an approach that can be used to structure the NPR in a risk-oriented manner. There are different ways of prioritising possible (chemical) food safety risks. A quantitative analysis of individual substances requires both time and budget, which are often only available to a limited extent (van Asselt et al., 2013; van der Fels-Klerx et al., 2015; Van der Fels-Klerx et al., 2018). Decision trees or expert judgement appear to be the best alternatives for prioritising (chemical) substances with regard to food safety risks; this provides sufficient differentiation between substances on the basis of available data. For the prioritisation of substances, WFSR designed decision trees according to which substances can be classified with a high, medium or low priority (van Asselt et al., 2018a; van Asselt et al., 2018b). The classification is carried out on the basis of risks for food safety (probability x effect). The criteria are reproduced in table 1.

¹ Council Directive 96/22/EC of 29 April 1996 concerning the prohibition on the use in livestock farming of certain substances having a hormonal or thyreostatic action and of β -agonists, and repealing Directives 81/602/EEC, 88/146/EEC and 88/299/EEC

² Council Directive 96/23/EC on measures to monitor certain substances and residues thereof in live animals and animal products and repealing Directives 85/358/EEC and 86/469/EEC and Decisions 89/187/EEC and 91/664/EEC.

³ Regulation (EU) 2017/625 on official controls and other official activities performed to ensure the application of food and feed law, rules on animal health and welfare, plant health and plant protection products, amending Regulations (EC) No 999/2001, (EC) No 396/2005, (EC) No 1069/2009, (EC) No 1107/2009, (EU) No 1151/2012, (EU) No 652/2014, (EU) 2016/429 and (EU) 2016/2031 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Regulations (EC) No 1/2005 and (EC) No 1099/2009 and Council Directives 98/58/EC, 1999/74/EC, 2007/43/EC, 2008/119/EC and 2008/120/EC, and repealing Regulations (EC) No 854/2004 and (EC) No 882/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Directives 89/608/EEC, 89/662/EEC, 90/425/EEC, 91/496/EEC, 96/23/EC, 96/93/EC and 97/78/EC and Council Decision 92/438/EEC (Official Controls Regulation).

⁴ Wageningen Food Safety Research, up to 1-6-2019 RIKILT

The accompanying decision trees can be found in annex 1. Substances classified high deserve more attention in the monitoring programme than substances classified medium or low. BuRO subsequently advised the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (NVWA) about the structure of the NPR and on the layout of the monitoring (BuRO, 2018;2019).

Office for Risk Assessment & Research

Date
15 October 2020

Table 1. Criteria in decision trees that are used to classify substances on the basis of food safety risks.

Our Ref.
TRCVWA/2020/5382

criteria used in the decision trees	group I prohibited substances	group II contaminants	group III authorised veterinary medicinal products
Is there an action limit, MRL/ML ⁵ ?		X	X
Limit exceeded in the last 5 years	X	X	X
Use (or probability thereof)	X		X
Scientific information about risks to humans	X	X	
Length of waiting period			X
Limit exceeded in animal feed in the last 5 years		X	
Transfer of substance to animal product		X	
Essential for human application?			x

In response to the WFSR study and the BuRO advice and in advance of the coming into effect of Regulation (EU) 2017/625, the National Residues Plan working group of the NVWA asked BuRO to "issue advice on how the NPR can be restructured in a risk-oriented manner, taking into account the space afforded by the new Official Control Regulation (EU) 2017/625 and the previously issued advice by RIKILT⁶." In 2019, BuRO first published an advice in which the above question was answered (BuRO, 2019) In the current advice, the same substances are classified as in the first advice. These are the following substance groups: antimicrobial agents⁷ (including sulfonamides and quinolones; group B1 in Regulation 2017/625), antiparasitic agents (group B2), carbamates (group B4) and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs; group B6).

Approach

BuRO requested WFSR to apply the previously designed decision trees to a number of substance groups and animals/animal products. Following on from BuRO advice from 2019 and in collaboration with the National Residues Plan working group in products of animal origin of the NVWA, the decision was taken to once again classify the antimicrobial agents, antiparasitic agents, carbamates and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). On this occasion, however, in combination with the remaining animals/animal products. This decision was based on the fact that these are the substance groups with the highest number of samples and analyses in the current NPR. In addition to the previous investigation, this time the decision was taken to classify the following animals/animal products: horse, goat, sheep and milk. In the past, for the same substance group, a classification was made for the other animals/animal products (cattle, pigs, poultry and eggs) (BuRO, 2019; van Asselt et al., 2019).

⁵ Statutory limit for levels in food products. MRL: Maximum Residue Limit for residues of veterinary medicinal products; ML: Maximum Limit for environmental contaminants.

⁶ RIKILT merged (on 1-6-2019) with the Laboratory for Feed and Food Safety of the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (NVWA) under the name [Wageningen Food Safety Research](#) (WFSR).

⁷Antimicrobial agents⁷ VO(including sulfonamides and quinolones; group B1 in Regulation 2017/625, antiparasitic agents (group B2), carbamates (group B4) and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs; group B6).

One of the selection criteria in the decision trees is the actual use of agents. To obtain this information, BuRO contacted the trade association of Manufacturers and Importers of Veterinary Medicines (FIDIN) and the Netherlands Veterinary Medicines Institute (SDa). Both FIDIN and the SDa supplied the requested information directly to WFSR.

For a risk-oriented structure, the focus of the advice is on the choice of substances according to the classification on the basis of decision trees, and the choice of a suitable matrix (urine, blood, meat, kidney, liver). The question of how many samples should be taken is not considered in this advice. This requires a separate study, because the answer depends heavily on the purpose of the control (identifying violations of the standard, determining prevalence, satisfying legislation that relates to the number of samples to production volume).

Findings

- Figures 1 to 4 provide an overview per substance group of the number of substances classified low, medium or high for horse, goat, sheep and milk (for the classification of all individual substances see (van Asselt et al., 2020) and Appendix I). For the NSAIDs, certain substances were classified as 'start survey'. This applies to substances about which insufficient information was available, about possible use (Appendix I, decision tree III).

Figure 1. An overview of the number of low, medium or high classified antibiotics (substances) for horse, goat, sheep and milk. Classification 'high' was awarded to those antibiotics considered essential for human use (independently of the use in animal/animal product).

Office for Risk Assessment & Research

Date
15 October 2020

Our Ref.
TRCVWA/2020/5382

Figure 2. An overview of the number of low, medium or high classified antiparasitic agents (substances) for horse, goat, sheep and milk. In the category unspecified, no distinction could be made according to animal type or animal product because no animal-specific data about residue concentrations (not non-compliant) of these prohibited antiparasitic agents have been reported.

Figure 3. An overview of the number of low, medium or high classified carbamates (substances). In the category unspecified, no distinction could be made according to animal type or animal product because no animal-specific data about residue concentrations (not non-compliant) of these prohibited carbamates have been reported.

Figure 4. An overview of the number of low, medium or high classified NSAIDs (substances) for horse, goat, sheep and milk.

- Generally speaking, there are missing datasets for the investigated animal types/animal products. This results in an 'unknown' route in the decision tree. Missing and/or incomplete datasets:
 - No structural data are available from SDA about the use of antibiotics in horse, goat and sheep. The data available on the use of antibiotics in dairy cows are not specific because these also include use in young cattle.
 - Sales figures for other groups of veterinary medicinal products (antiparasitic agents, carbamates and NSAIDs) could almost entirely not be specified according to the evaluated animal types because these veterinary medicinal products generally have a registration for cattle. The sales figures for these veterinary medicinal products probably relate primarily to cattle, but here too, a reservation must be made in respect of milk, since no distinction can be made between use in dairy and meat cows.

EFSA monitoring data relating to residues of veterinary medicinal products in sheep and goat make no distinction between the two animal types.
- Because there are particularly few veterinary medicinal products with a registration for the treatment of diseases in goats, sheep and horses, it is probable that in practice, the cascade regulation will often be applied. If use is made of the cascade regulation, and no waiting period is specified for that agent, a standard waiting period applies (7 days for milk and 28 days for meat) in respect of which it is not always whether this is long enough for the particular substance-animal combination.
- In the framework of the prescription of veterinary medicinal products for food-producing animals, horses form a 'separate' animal type because unlike pigs and cattle, for example, these animals are not primarily intended as food-producing animals, in the Netherlands. If horses are nevertheless intended for human consumption, a number of specific veterinary medicinal products require additional attention:
 - buprenorphine, acepromazine and guaifenesin⁸; treated horses may not be slaughtered for human consumption.
 - performance-enhancing agents (prohibited) that are administered to (sports) horses.
 - pergolide, used chronically for the treatment of horses with Cushing's disease.
- At present, carbamates are determined in meat, while liver would be a better matrix for analysis. For the other substance groups, there are no indications that the analysis matrix needs to be changed.

**Office for Risk Assessment
& Research**

Date
15 October 2020

Our Ref.
TRCVWA/2020/5382

Answer to the question

How can the NPR be restructured in a risk-oriented manner, taking into account the space afforded by the new Official Control Regulation (EU) 2017/625 and the previously issued advice by RIKILT?

The tables drawn up by WFSR with low, medium or high classification can be used for a risk-oriented choice of substances for the structuring of the NPR by the directorate Inspection of the NVWA.

The NPR can be structured in a risk-oriented manner, in respect of choice of substances, by opting for substance-animal/animal product combinations

⁸ These agents appear on the 'positive list' from Regulation (EU) 122/2013. After a waiting period of six months, these horses may be slaughtered for human consumption. In the Netherlands, the Medicines Evaluation Board (CBG) has specified the waiving of this regulation so that treated horses may not be slaughtered for human consumption.

classified by WFSR as high and medium. For the classification of all individual substances, see van Asselt et al., 2020.

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Advice from BuRO

To the Head of Agency

- Use the classification of substance-animal/animal product combination as reported in the advice for a risk-oriented substance choice in structuring the NPR. In doing so, be aware of possible risks that can occur in using specific veterinary medicinal products in horses and in the use of the cascade regulation for goats, sheep and horses.
- Also make a classification for the remaining substance groups for all animal types/animal products as specified for the NPR, so that a risk-oriented choice can also be made for these remaining substances. Evaluate the classification of the substance animal/animal product combinations regularly.
- Focus on making structural agreements with FIDIN and SDa in the field of data interchange.

Date

15 October 2020

Our Ref.

TRCVWA/2020/5382

Yours sincerely,

Office for Risk Assessment & Research
Prof. Antoon Opperhuizen

Appendix 1. Decision trees

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Group I - Prohibited substances

Date
15 October 2020

Our Ref.
TRCVWA/2020/5382

Group II – Contaminants

Office for Risk Assessment & Research

Date
15 October 2020

Our Ref.
TRCVWA/2020/5382

Group III – Authorised substances EU

Office for Risk Assessment & Research

Date
15 October 2020

Our Ref.
TRCVWA/2020/5382

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Office for Risk Assessment
& Research

Date
15 October 2020

Our Ref.
TRCVWA/2020/5382